

Electoral Manipulation and Women's Rights in Autocracies

Marwa Shalaby

Marwa Shalaby is an Assistant Professor in the Political Science department at the University of Wisconsin-Madison. She is the author of the forthcoming book Varieties of Power: Women's Political Representation in Autocratic Legislatures (Columbia University Press 2025). Email: marwa.shalaby@wisc.edu.

Recent work has brought to light the alarming rise of a “wave of patriarchal authoritarianism” and called attention to its adverse effects on women’s hard-earned gains (Chenoweth and Marks 2022). This issue is further complicated, given the increased levels of democratic backsliding across the globe (Lührmann and Lindberg 2019). Notwithstanding the ongoing debate about whether democratic backsliding is a reality or a perception that is partly driven by a feedback loop between the coding experts and the media (Little and Meng 2024, Willick 2023), my work on gender politics in the Middle East and North Africa autocracies provides evidence that the effects of democratic backsliding are highly gendered.

Bermeo (2016, 6) argues that “forms of democratic backsliding are legitimated through the very institutions that democracy promoters have prioritized” and views strategic election manipulation¹ as a form of backsliding. I identify a similar trend in Jordan, whereby autocrats’ election manipulation has gendered effects that have curtailed women’s equitable access to political power. The monarchy in Jordan promulgated the political

parties’ law in 1992, granting individuals the right to form parties and field candidates for elections. However, the regime also enforced the single non-transferable vote (SNTV) (aka the one-man, one-vote) law of 1993 aimed at limiting the role of the Islamists after their overwhelming victory in 1989. Thus, the electoral arena was transformed for more than two decades by engineering an electoral landscape that continued to favor tribal and pro-regime figures while further weakening the influence of political parties and other marginalized, less organized groups—mainly women. During this period, only one woman could win a legislative seat until the introduction of gender quotas in 2003.²

The SNTV system remained untouched until the introduction of the election law changes of June 2012, which stipulated one additional national closed-list district with 27 extra seats open for party candidates. For the first time, women were able to win *three* non-reserved seats from the newly added national list— in addition to the 15 reserved seats. In 2016, the electoral law changed again, and SNTV was replaced with an open-list PR system (Esber and Hussainy 2017). It also reduced the

1 According to Bermeo (2016, 13), strategic manipulation denotes a range of actions aimed at tilting the electoral playing field in favor of the incumbent.

2 In 2003, six out of 110 seats were reserved for women. The seats increased to twelve and fifteen in 2010 and 2013, respectively (Shalaby, Forthcoming).

number of seats in Parliament from 150 to 130, and the number of electoral districts decreased from 45 to 23, but the number of reserved seats for women (15 seats) remained unchanged. Remarkably, women could win five non-reserved seats in 2016 (in addition to the reserved seats). In the 2020 elections, elites manipulated the system to limit women's gains beyond the reserved quota seats. Ma'ayeh and Sweis (2021, 4) argued that "several male candidates in the 2020 elections were reluctant to include politically astute females in their lists, fearing they would win through direct competition, as few did in 2016." As a result, women were unable to win any non-reserved seats in 2020.

The case of Jordan shows us how, while gender quota mechanisms can remedy some of the gendered effects of backsliding, the instability and manipulation of the electoral landscape may have detrimental effects on women's equitable access to political power.

Finally, it is important to remind ourselves that the strategies adopted by autocratic regimes to stifle reforms are ever-changing and constantly in flux. Autocrats employ techniques ranging from electoral manipulation, cooptation, and offering controlled openings (and closures) in response to contemporaneous events and external and domestic demands and threats. Importantly, autocrats are also facing rising domestic pressures. In addition to the increase of women in politics over the past few decades, there have been remarkable achievements in health and education outcomes for women. Women are also entering the workforce in increasing numbers. Despite the long-standing political stagnation and absence of political reforms/democratization, a massive societal transformation is occurring. It will be interesting to see how these societal forces can counter

incumbents' backsliding efforts. ♦

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